

**Conceptual framework for ensuring sustainable development of regions and
efficient use of water resources**

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Abstract : This publication presents the conceptual framework for sustainable development of regions and ensuring the efficient use of water resources, as well as problems arising in the process of socio-economic development of the region.

Key words : sustainable development, water shortage, efficient use of water resources, economic policy.

The concept of sustainable development interprets the idea of economic and social development of regions without destroying the natural environment and ensuring its integrity with other elements. The regional economic policy of any country covers scientific issues of sustainable and balanced development with the rational use of social, economic and environmental factors.

Regional economic policy is a set of measures that have a direct impact on the location of productive forces in order to create conditions for stable economic development [1]. It is important to systematize many factors, such as capital, natural and economic resources, production and social infrastructure, qualified personnel, based on the concept of sustainable development of the region with the rational placement of productive forces in the regions.

It is known that many opinions have been expressed regarding the goals and directions of the state's regional economic policy in the field of sustainable development of regions. In particular, a group of researchers expressed the opinion that “the country's regional economic policy should ensure a relatively uniform and reasonable distribution of productive forces based on the formation of an intercompatible system of production and social infrastructure” [2].

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In a number of scientific sources, the issue of rational use of natural resources is mentioned as one of the main goals of the country's regional policy.

It is important to pay attention to the quality, scale and rational use of natural resources when determining the objectives of regional economic policy pursued in the country and the causes of regional inequality [3].

Indeed, in the sustainable development of regions it is necessary to pay serious attention to aspects of the quality and scale of use of natural resources. For example, the relevance of the issue of efficient use of land and water resources while ensuring interregional environmental balance is characterized by the lack of possibility of increasing their quantity from internal sources. If these current problems are considered from the point of view of the Syr Darya and Amu Darya basins, it becomes clear that they have specific regional aspects.

In the conditions of modern water scarcity, the task is to ensure the sustainable development of the region by solving the complex problem of meeting the water and energy needs of a growing population, industrial and agricultural production.

At the same time, water resources remain one of the main factors not only in the socio-economic development of a network or region, but also in their formation. Based on this, we can say that water shortage in the basin, high water consumption in production, water ecology and transboundary problems are all issues that require serious attention in the country's regional policy.

Changes in the world economy in recent years, new industrialization and modernization of the economy show that attention is paid to theoretical and methodological issues of the concept of sustainable development.

Sustainable development is a direction that focuses on preserving the natural environment and expanded reproductive potential for a long period of time, balancing the elements of the ecological, social and economic system of society. “The concept of sustainable development reflects the balance between social needs, economic and environmental opportunities to ensure the stability of society and improve the quality of life of people.” Based on this, we can say that the main task of the system of economic sciences today is to assimilate the ideas of sustainable development and develop, on this basis, theoretical directions for the development of economic management mechanisms. One of the central provisions of the concept of sustainable development is that when using nature, it is emphasized not to deprive its elements of regeneration capabilities. The first paradigm for the concept of sustainable development

was given by the Canadian Environmental Commission in 1915: “Each generation has the right to use a certain part of the natural capital, i.e. their percentage, therefore the main part of natural capital must be transferred to the next generation intact and intact” [4,5]. According to this, humanity will have to live off a percentage of natural resources.

As mentioned above, one of the main conditions for sustainable development is the rational and efficient use of regional water resources. Theoretically, establishing the efficient use of water resources in the regions is within the framework of theoretical-ideological, scientific-practical, regional tasks. Internal problems include inefficient use of water resources in the regions and deterioration of the infrastructure system to such an extent that it does not meet competitive requirements, as well as technogenic and anthropogenic impacts.

External factors mainly include effects associated with changes in the flow regime of transboundary rivers and the hydrological regime of large reservoirs, as well as water distribution problems arising from the mutual use of water. Theoretical and methodological mechanisms for efficient water use should be aimed at ensuring sustainability by assessing these problems and reducing their consequences.

A group of researchers recommended ideas for achieving macroeconomic stability mainly through structural and institutional improvement of the water management network and increasing the efficiency of water use in economic sectors.

In particular, in the sustainable development of regions, the application of ideas for managing water needs will have a great effect in the regions by improving the system of standards for the efficient use of water, achieving efficiency through specialization in industries with low water consumption in Uzbekistan. In fact, scientific conclusions were obtained by analyzing the state of water use within the agricultural sector, where a lot of water is consumed.

Based on the above considerations and scientific approaches, it would be advisable if the concepts of effective and rational use of water resources were defined as follows:

“Efficient use of water resources” means the maximum efficiency of each unit of water used, taking into account future needs;

“Rational use of water resources” means the economical use of surface and underground water sources without disturbing the mutual balance of natural elements.

In this case, it is necessary to start saving in the rational use of water, taking into account the needs of the environment and wildlife in the river basin itself. Then the balance in nature will not be disrupted. Having taken water from the source, we must

think about how to benefit from every drop of it. Rational use is established in the river basin, and efficient use is established in irrigated areas. This is the only way we will establish efficient use of water resources in the regions based on the ideas of sustainable development. Therefore, in the new edition of the concept of sustainable development of Uzbekistan, along with the above points, it is appropriate to seriously consider the territorial features of the country. The concepts of “Sustainable Development” and “Green Economy” can become the theoretical basis for the formation of a new way of efficient and rational use of water in the regions. In turn, it is necessary to establish efficient use of water resources for stable socio-economic development of the regions.

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